

Removal of Arsenic (III) and Arsenic (V) from Aqueous Solutions by Different Adsorbents

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INTRODUCTION

The traditional reputation of arsenic as a poison is largely due to the higher toxicity of the As(III) ion, whereas elemental arsenic (As[V]) and organic arsenic compounds are commonly considered less toxic.

The normal amount of arsenic in hair is 0.08-0.25 mg/kg, whereas 1 mg/kg is an indication of toxicity. The normal amount of arsenic in nails is 0.043-1.08 mg/kg. The normal amount of arsenic in urine is 0.005-0.40 mg/kg (1.5 D). The maximum permissible limit of arsenic in drinking water is 0.05 mg/L. Widespread arsenic contamination has been found in different regions of West Bengal due to dissolution of arsenic-containing bedrock. The high arsenic content of the drinking water has become a major public health issue in six districts of West Bengal in India, where an estimated 30 million people dependent on tubewell water sources have been adversely affected. The districts are in the eastern sector of West Bengal, extending 450 km from north to south bordering Bangladesh. The severely affected districts are Malda, Murshidabad, Nadia, Bardhaman, 24 Parganas (North), and 24 Parganas (South). The arsenic content in the groundwater ranges from 0.01 to 0.59 mg/L in as many as 830 villages in this area. Tubewells have been dug to a depth of 120 to 50 feet. Table 1a shows the arsenic levels in drinking water in West Bengal, and Table 1b shows a study of arsenic level in the tissue and body fluid of the people of West Bengal (Chakraborty et al., 1999).

Most water treatment technologies suitable for developed countries are expensive for towns and small industries of developing countries because of limitation of funds and lack of skilled labor. The process of adsorption has an edge over other methods, due

TABLE 1a. Occurrence of arsenic in the groundwater of West Bengal

8 districts/830 villages in 58 blocks Total samples analyzed: 34,900	Concentration of As in water (mg/L)		
	<0.01	>0.05	>0.01
	43.5%	38.7%	56.5%

TABLE 1b. Study arsenic level in the human tissue (mg/kg) and body fluid (µg/1.5 D) of the people of West Bengal

	Total Samples Analyzed	% of Samples Above Normal Level
Hair	3,530	74.0
Nails	3,620	74.0
Skin	163	[1.2-29.3]
Urine	7,240	83.6

to its simplicity and sludge-free clean operation. There is an increasing search for low-cost adsorbent material made from locally available waste material and plant substrata (Table 2). Some low-cost adsorbents that selectively remove As(III) and As(V) have been tested in the laboratory by batch and column technique; pH, concentration, flowrate, and breakthrough capacity have been investigated.

TABLE 2. Adsorbents for removal of As(III) and As(V) from water

Adsorbent	Reference
Ferric sulphide bed	Lee et al., 1972
Bauxite sample	Balient Ambro, 1974
Chitin mixture	Elson C.M. et al., 1980
Amorphous iron oxide	Pierce et al., 1982
Manganese dioxide soil	D.W. Huang, 1983
Lake sediments	Takamastu, 1985
Coal fly ash	Sen A.K. and Arnab K. De, 1987
Coral limestone	Shigeru, 1992
Activated carbon impregnated with metallic Ag, Cu	Rajakovic, 1992
Ganga sand	Vaishaya R.C., 1993
Synthetic birnessite	Scott, 1995
Basic yttrium carbonate	Wasay et al., 1996
Iron-coated spent catalyst	Liu J.C. and Huang, 1997
Chemically treated sawdust	Nag, A., 1998
Manganese dioxide-coated sand	Sanjeev Bajpai, 1999
Lanthanum-impregnated sawdust carbon	Raji C. Anirudhan, 1999
Ferric oxide-impregnated carbon	Brian Reed, 2000

INDUSTRIES RELEASING ARSENIC

Arsenic is used in the metallurgical industry, glassware and ceramic industries, dye and pesticide manufacturing industries, and petroleum refineries. Chemicals containing arsenic are used in the manufacture of herbicides and pesticides. In West Bengal, a factory manufacturing acetocopper arsenite, a pesticide, polluted drinking water in the southern part of Calcutta. Arsenic is released into the surface water through mining and burning of coal as well as copper smelting. Rivers flowing through the coal fields of Bihar have been reported to carry large amounts of arsenic, responsible for downstream arsenic poisoning in West Bengal. According to studies, the arsenic contamination of the Damodar in West Bengal is mainly due to dumping wastes from the coal mines along the river bed (Susheela, 1999).

HEALTH HAZARDS DUE TO HIGH ARSENIC INTAKE

As(III) ion causes arsenicosis in human beings. Symptoms of arsenic poisoning are abdominal pains, vomiting, diarrhea, and pain in the extremities, followed later by numbness and tingling of the extremities, palmoplantar hyperkeratosis, Mees lines on the fingernails, and deterioration in motor and sensory responses. Symptoms of chronic arsenicalism include dermal lesions, peripheral neuropathy, skin cancer, and peripheral

vascular disease. Bony fish and freshwater mussels contain a high content of arsenic (Table 3).

TABLE 3. Arsenic content of some food items

Food items	As (ppm)
Bony fish	2-8
Oyster	3-10
Mussels	120
Shrimp	42
Prawns	174
Cows milk	0.03-0.06
Vegetables	0.001

As, Hg, Pb, Cd are highly toxic even at low concentrations. Zn(II) in some metallo-enzymes is substituted by Cd(II). Arsenic acts on the biological system in the following ways: Toxic As(III) inhibits enzyme activity by reacting with ligands containing sulphhydryl (-SH) groups. As(III) attacks -SH groups of an enzyme (i.e., inactivation of pyruvic dehydrogenase by complexation with As[III]), preventing the generation of ATP in the citric acid cycle. Pyruvic dehydrogenase is highly sensitive to arsenic because of its interaction with two -SH groups of lipoic acid, leading to pyruvate accumulation. As(III) ion readily crosses the placental barrier and causes fetal damage. Arsenic when absorbed in the biological system can undergo bio-transformation under *in vivo* conditions, as the As(V) ion, or arsenate, can be reduced to the As(III) form, or arsenite. The half-life of this bio-transformed arsenite is three to five days, when it can cause harm to the system (Susheela, 1999).

Arsenicosis is a chronic disease with a significant latency period for non-cancer and cancer effects. There appears to be discrepancy in the literature regarding latency, with some reports of 2 years being the minimum for hyperpigmentation and keratosis. Researchers in Bangladesh suggest that 5 years is the minimum latency, whilst some other estimates suggest that this is 9 years. Latency for cancers is also unknown, but it is estimated to be of the order of 20 years. The proportion of a population exposed to elevated arsenic that will develop arsenicosis is uncertain, but may be significant. Medical treatments for arsenicosis are not fully developed. There is an indication that switching to arsenic-safe water and anti-oxidants may reverse symptoms in early stages. The proportion of a population exposed to elevated arsenic from drinking water that will go on to develop arsenicosis is unknown.

The World Health organization (WHO) has modeled the progression of arsenicosis using data from Samta, Bangladesh. The range of those affected over 30 years was 15.75% in the lowest estimate scenario to 29.25% in the highest estimate scenario. Variation in the estimates of mortality from cancers was between 5.0 and 6.5%. This implies a significant overall health burden for those affected. It is not clear whether early removal of arsenic-contaminated water would reduce the onset of cancers, but it is assumed that it would have some impact because of the cumulative nature of the risk.

More recent work suggests that anti-oxidants within vitamins A, C, and E and possibly compounds containing zinc and selenium also work to reverse symptoms. A

recent controlled trial was performed in Bangladesh, but this remains to be published and may require further controlled clinical trials. However, this does indicate the necessity of combining both environmental and medical interventions for arsenicosis (Howard, 2003).

PREPARATION OF ADSORBENTS

Washed and dried river Ganga sand (geometric mean size 0.49 mm) was washed with distilled water until the runoff was clear, dried, and stored.

Manganese dioxide-coated sand was prepared by forming manganese dioxide by oxidation of manganous ion by permanganate in presence of sand. First, 250 g of washed and dried river sand (geometric mean size 0.49 mm) was added to 250 mL 0.1 M KMnO_4 solution. Next, 250 mL of 0.4 M NaOH was added to make the pH alkaline, and 250 mL 0.3 M MnCl_2 was added dropwise while the mixture was mixed in magnetic stirrer. The coated sand was washed with distilled water until the runoff was clear, dried, and stored (Bajpai and Chaudhari, 1999).

The method was adopted for Fe(III) hydroxide impregnation on coal. Bituminous coal crushed to geometric mean size of 0.102 mm was washed several times with distilled water and dried in the oven. The proximate analysis of coal was moisture at (60% RH) 4.7%, ash 18.2%, volatile 32.0%, and fixed carbon 45.1%. 20 g of coal were slurried in 100 mL distilled water to which 2 g of Fe(III) chloride was added. Using 2 N sodium hydroxide solution, the pH was then adjusted to 11.5 and the volume made up to 200 mL. The slurry was allowed to settle for 24 hours. The adsorbent following pretreatment/impregnation was removed, washed several times with distilled water, dried, and desiccated (Lal, 1992).

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Stock solutions were prepared using AR-grade sodium arsenate and sodium arsenite in distilled and tap water. 0.1 M KOH and 0.2 M HCl used to adjust the pH. Batch adsorption studies were performed in glass-stoppered conical flasks at room temperature in rotary shaker. Column studies were done using 1.25 ID glass column loaded with adsorbent, and As(III) and As(V) was percolated downward at a flowrate of ~5 mL/minute. The operation was stopped when arsenic was detected in effluent (break-through point). Arsenic was determined in the test solutions spectrophotometrically using a Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer (NEERI, 1997).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ganga sand can be used as a low-cost adsorbent for treating As(III) at low levels. The removal of As(III) was determined to be 85 $\mu\text{g/g}$ for initial concentration of 1.6 mg/L at an adsorbent dose of 20 g/L. Adsorption of As(III) on Ganga sand is pH-dependent, and maximum percent removal occurs between pH 7-9, followed by a marginal decrease at pH range 9-12 (Figure 1). As(III) is found in aqueous form in the form of arsenious acid, an undissociated weak acid with no charge. The uptake of As(III) may be due to a combination of electrostatic attraction between sorbate and sorbents, and of van der Waals attraction. Column studies were done at 0.8 mg As(III)/L concentration in tap water, which produced arsenic levels below the WHO guideline value for arsenic. Sodium hydroxide is an efficient regenerant chemical for removing arsenic from Ganga sand.

FIGURE 1. As(III) removal by Ganga sand

For manganese dioxide-coated sand (Figure 2), arsenite is oxidized to arsenate by manganese dioxide ($\text{H}_3\text{AsO}_3 + \text{MnO}_2 = \text{HAsO}_4^{2-} + \text{Mn}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$); the released Mn^{2+} adsorbs on the manganese dioxide, giving it a positive surface and leading to an enhancement in the removal/adsorption of arsenate present initially or produced as a result of arsenite oxidation. The performance of manganese dioxide-coated sand in arsenic removal in 10 cycles in column experiment was good (0.5 mg As[III]/L, 0.5 mg As[V]/L influent) with no As(III) or Mn(II) leaching in the effluent. Breakthrough volume was at WHO guideline 0.01 mg/L, and 85% arsenic was recovered during regeneration.

For Fe(III) hydroxide-impregnated coal (Figure 3), anionic As(V) removal decreased with increasing pH, whereas As(III) removal is not a strong function of pH, increased to maximum at pH ~7. As(V) and As(III) form inner sphere complexes with iron hydroxide. As(V) speciation between pH 4-10, $\text{H}_2\text{AsO}_4^- = \text{HAsO}_4^{2-} + \text{H}^+$ pKa = 7, at

FIGURE 2. Removal of As(III), As(V) by MnO₂-coated sand

FIGURE 3. Removal of As(III) and As(V) by iron oxide-impregnated coal

this pH range the net surface is negative, producing a repulsive electrostatic force between HAsO_4^{2-} and adsorbent. The chemical interaction force must be greater than the repulsive electrostatic force for removal to occur. As(III) in pH range 3-11, $\text{H}_3\text{AsO}_3 = \text{H}_2\text{AsO}_3^- + \text{H}^+$ $\text{pK}_a = 9.2$, the predominant species is H_3AsO_3 , the electrostatic force is zero, and the removal is attributed to chemical interactions (inner sphere complexation) at $\text{pH} \sim 8.5$. About 20% of the aqueous As(III) exists as H_2AsO_4^- , a repulsive electrostatic force exists; this repulsive electrostatic force contributes to the decrease in removal with increasing pH (Reed et al., 2000).

Fe(III) hydroxide-loaded coal was used as an adsorbent for As(V) and As(III). Fe(III) coexisted in the aqueous solution; the presence of Cl^- , NO_2^- , SO_4^{2-} , CH_3COO^- had no effect, but PO_4^{3-} greatly decreased the adsorption (Shigeru et al., 1992).

As(III) adsorption on lanthanum-impregnated sawdust carbon (Figure 4) increased 10.3%-86.0% by increasing the pH from 1.0-12 for the initial concentration of 50 mg/L. The anionic forms H_2AsO_3^- and HAsO_3^{2-} are the predominant species in this pH range. It seems that the chemical reaction and the less soluble precipitates LaHAsO_3 or $\text{La}(\text{OH})\text{H}_2\text{AsO}_3$ on the carbon surface was most likely adsorption process, the predominant species is H_3AsO_3 in this acid range.

Impregnation of activated carbon by metallic Cu improves the sorption process for As(III) in pH range 4-9, which is the optimum pH for apparent affinity between the carbon surface and the arsenic species H_3AsO_3 and H_2AsO_4^- predominant at this pH (Rajakovic et al., 1992).

A strong anion exchange resin DOWEX-1X8 can be used to separate a mixture of As(V) and As(III) anions at pH 7.7 (Table 4a). As(III) is present as unionized H_3AsO_3

FIGURE 4. As(III) removal by lanthanum-impregnated sawdust carbon

while As(V) is present as $H_2AsO_4^-$ and $HAsO_4^-$ anions, which are retained on the resin bed and eluted from the column with 0.1 M HCl. Toxic As(III) can be oxidized to As(V) by chlorinated water and removed (Table 4b).

A study indicated that arsenic in a concentration of 80 $\mu\text{g/L}$ or more results in dialysis, dementia, and risk of Alzheimer's disease (Gupta et al., 1999). Activated alumina could achieve greater than 95% As(V) and As(III) removal twice as effectively as activated bauxite and 12 times more effectively than activated carbon. Activated alumina removed As(V) over 20 times more effectively than As(III) along with fluoride at pH 5.0. The adsorption of As(V) on alumina is governed by the diffusion within the particles; better adsorption capacity can be achieved by standing the adsorption process for more

TABLE 4a. Recovery of arsenic from a mixture of As(III) and As(V) in different ratios after separation through anion exchange column

As(III)	As(V)	As(III)	As(V)
Taken (μg)		Recovered (μg)	
2.0	0	1.8	0.01
0.0	1.8	0.01	1.9
1.0	0.45	0.95	0.5
1.4	0.35	1.4	0.35
0.4	0.25	0.3	0.35
0.2	0.35	0.1	0.35
0.2	0.2	0.15	0.2
0.1	0.09	0.1	0.1
0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05
0.02	0.02	0.015	0.015

TABLE 4b. Recovery of As(V) from As(III) after oxidation with Cl₂ water and passing ion exchange column

Amount of As(III) (µg)	Amount of Cl ₂ water added (mL)	Amount of As(V) (µg)	% Recovery
100	0.0	0	0
100	2.0	92	92
100	4.0	90	90
100	8.0	89	89

than 12 hours. The smaller the particle size, the better will be the kinetic performance. Activated alumina can be regenerated by 4-5% NaOH, and 70% capacity can be regenerated after first use (Ghosh et al., 1987).

CONCLUSION

Ganga sand and manganese dioxide-coated sand are better low-cost adsorbents than others. Both show promise for cheap and effective removal of As(V) and As(III) from water.

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